

Combining Radiative Cooling and Light Trapping Strategies for Improved Performance of PERC Bifacial Silicon Solar Cells

UNAI URDIROZ,^{1,2} IÑIGO ITOIZ,³ JOAQUÍN SEVILLA,^{4,5} AND ANGEL ANDUEZA^{4,5,*}

¹Dpto. Ingeniería, Universidad Pública de Navarra, 31006 Pamplona, Spain

²Institute for Advanced Materials (INAMAT), Universidad Pública de Navarra, 31006 Pamplona, Spain

³Solafam Ingeniería, 31006 Pamplona, Navarra.

⁴Dpto. Ing. Eléctrica, Electrónica y de Comunicación, Universidad Pública de Navarra, 31006 Pamplona, Spain

⁵Smart Cities Institute (SCI), Universidad Pública de Navarra, 31006 Pamplona, Spain

[*angel.andueza@unavarra.es](mailto:angel.andueza@unavarra.es)

KEYWORDS

Texturing, Radiative cooling, Light trapping, Bifacial solar cell, PERC, Antireflective

HIGHLIGHTS

- Design of PERC panels combining Radiative Cooling and Light Trapping Strategies.
- Inverted pyramids textures on silicon to enhance light trapping in silicon
- Glass texturing to reduce the nominal operating temperature.
- Texturing from each face can be optimized independently.
- Texturing increases infrared absorption from the sun.
- The net power balance is negative if both strategies are applied simultaneously.

ABSTRACT

This work investigates the impact of combining light trapping and radiative cooling on bifacial solar panels. While several techniques have been proposed to enhance the efficiency of solar panels, their combination can lead to suboptimal results. By numerically evaluating the light absorption and thermal balance of different panel configurations, we found that each side of the bifacial solar cell can be textured independently with a cross-effect of less than 4%. However, our results also indicate that improving visible light trapping can increase infrared absorption, leading to a heating effect that may offset the benefits of radiative cooling. These findings highlight the importance of balancing the factors that influence solar panel efficiency and provide quantitative insights that guide the development of more effective solar energy systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing global demand for energy, coupled with the need to address the climate crisis and promote economic development, has spurred significant interest in the search for new renewable energy sources over the past few decades [1]. Since 2010, solar energy has become the third renewable energy source, behind hydropower and wind [2]. Among solar technologies, non-concentrated photovoltaic (PV) solar panels are the most commonly used for generating electrical energy [3].

Improving the efficiency of PV systems has been a primary goal in recent years, with a wide range of approaches being explored. On the one hand, various strategies have been proposed to maximize light absorption, including the use of transparent contacts [4,5], Silicon texturization [6,7], antireflective coatings [8,9] or bifacial systems [10,11], which are among the most promising. Bifacial solar cells (BSC) allow for light absorption through both the front (direct light) and rear (albedo) faces, resulting in up to 30% improvement in energy efficiency [12]. With production costs similar to those of monofacial cells [10] bifacial cells are expected to capture 70% of the PV market share by 2030, compared with 20% in 2020, according to the international technology roadmap [13] The role of the albedo in the efficiency of the cell has been recently studied [14,15].

Although a lot of advances are being made in perovskite technology [16], including optimizing light trapping in bifacial cells [17,18], PERC technology has become the main options in the photovoltaic market due to its interesting cost and efficiency [19]. A lot of research is being conducted recently in the improvement of the efficiency of these cells, for example to reduce recombination tailoring the passivation layer [19], rear contacts design and optimization for bifacial use [20–22], selective emitter design and optimization [23–25]. On the other hand, strategies have also been proposed to reduce the operating temperature of PV cells and improve their efficiency in recent years [26,27], including airflow cooling methods [28,29], photovoltaic-thermal collectors (PV/T) [30,31], water spraying [32] or radiative cooling [33] among others This temperature reduction directly impacts the cell efficiency as much as 0.4% per °C. Radiative cooling of photovoltaic modules has been extensively investigated recently, in single sided silicon cells [34–36] and in bifacial cells [31,37,38]. The joint optimization of light trapping and radiative cooling has also been studied [39,40].

The purpose of this work is to go a step further studying the combined effect of light trapping and radiative cooling in bifacial PERC cells. To improve the both effects, we analyze different patterns for texturing the four surfaces of the panel: silicon and glass front and albedo sides. The main issue to address in this global optimization is the possible cross effects between the two sides of the bifacial panel. For example, if texturing increases the rear silicon surface to increase albedo absorption results in decreasing significantly the direct radiation, the net effect would be detrimental for solar cell efficiency.

There are three different spectral ranges relevant for the purpose of this work. First, to maximize photocurrent generated, a silicon cell has to absorb as much radiation as possible in the interval where it is converted in current, from 0.3 to 1.2 μm . Second, the emissivity of the cell must be maximized in the 8 to 13 μm interval, which corresponds to a nearly transparent region in the atmosphere and facilitates the radiative emission between the panel surface and outer space. Moreover, by attaining an emissivity close to 1 within the 16 to 25 μm range, the second window region can still be utilized despite its lower transmission characteristics. And third, there is an intermediate wavelength region from 1.2 to 5 μm where the sun still provides almost 164 W/m^2 but is useless for current production on silicon photovoltaic panels. The optical characteristics of the ideal panel would be (i) very low reflectivity in the visible range, (ii) very high one in the closer infrared (1.2 to 5 μm) and (iii) high emissivity in the thermal infrared window. In the rest of the paper we present computer calculations of different surface texturizations on PERC cell and the evaluation of the abovementioned desired characteristics. In the range of texturing patterns and sizes investigated, cross effects between sides are negligible. Besides, in general

terms, silicon texturing increases light trapping and glass texturing enhances radiative cooling, but the thermal gain due to the closer infrared window cannot be avoided.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section, we describe the materials and methods used to analyze light absorption and thermal radiation optimization on a bifacial PERC solar cell. It is important to note that all the results presented are numerical calculations.

2.1. BIFACIAL SOLAR CELL USED MODEL

In order to perform the simulations, we begin by defining a precise model of a solar cell with all materials and dimensions well established. We have used the 3D electromagnetic model of the PERC bifacial solar cell [41,42], as shown in Fig. 1, which is based on a standard low-doped crystalline Si (p bulk) 160 μm wafer. The top and rear surfaces of the silicon wafer have a 500 nm thick heavily doped n+ emitter and p+ back surface field (BSF) layer. The doping concentration of the bulk, the emitter, and the BSF layer were selected based on typical values [43], with concentrations of 1×10^{19} , 3.3×10^{20} , and $1.5 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, respectively. An anti-reflective coating (ARC) layer of Silicon Nitride (Si_3N_4), conformal with the surface of silicon, is considered between the silicon and encapsulation layer. The thickness of the ARC layer is 80 nm, which corresponds to the $\lambda/4$ matching section to maximize the absorption of the silicon wafer around a wavelength of 550 nm. Finally, both sides of the solar cell encapsulate with around 3.2 mm ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) and soda-lime-low-iron glass. The front and back contact fingers are not included in the 3D model since the simulated wavelengths are significantly shorter than the usual distance between contacts on commercial cells, which is around 2 mm [43].

Fig. 1. Schematic cross-section of the simplest modeled PERC Bifacial solar cell structure (the thickness of the layers is not drawn to scale).

2.2. SIMULATION TOOLS

The absorptivity and emissivity of the bifacial PERC solar cell is calculated across the visible, near-infrared (NIR), and mid-infrared (MIR) ranges using two simulation tools: Grating Diffraction Calculator (GD-Calc) and CST MICROWAVE STUDIO™. Each one calculates the absorptivity and

emissivity in a different wavelength region: GD-Calc for the visible, NIR, and short-wavelength MIR (from 0.3 to 8 μm), and CST for the long-wavelength MIR range from 8 μm to 25 μm .

GD-Calc is a software package developed by Kenneth C. Johnson and integrated into Matlab that uses rigorously coupled-wave analysis (RCWA) [44,45]. It is ideal for solar cell problems since it can simulate structures much larger than the shorter wavelength of the calculation. Note that the total thickness of the modeled PERC bifacial solar cell is around 6.6 mm, and the shortest wavelength simulated is 0.3 μm , differing by almost four orders of magnitude. We selected a spatial resolution of the simulator to obtain accurate results and a reasonable simulation time for each wavelength. For the textured regions in glass and silicon, and considering the micrometric texturing sizes, the minimum spatial resolution selected was 10 nm, while the spectral resolution was 5 nm. Since GD-Calc assumes infinite spatial and temporal coherence, it predicts interference phenomena that are not real. To reduce the ripple noise introduced by this artifact, obtained data were filtered with a Savitzky-Golay smoothing method (with a polynomial degree of 8).

CST MICROWAVE STUDIO™ is a commercial software package that uses the Finite Integration time-domain Method (FIM) [46] for electromagnetic field simulation in the microwave, terahertz, and optical range. We selected CST for its ability to provide highly accurate results within a short simulation time. In order to calculate the absorptivity of the bifacial solar cell from 8 to 25 μm , we used a frequency solver tool with tetrahedral adaptive mesh refinement. The textured glass unit cell has been modeled with an infinite thickness, assuming that all incident radiation is absorbed by the glass and not transmitted. This approach is consistent with the actual model, given that the thickness of the glass (3.2 mm) is much larger than the MIR wavelength range, which corresponds to atmospheric windows.

The simulations were based on refractive index data for the materials used, which were obtained from the scientific literature. Further information on the refractive index and albedo models used in the presented calculations can be found in the Supplementary Materials section [47].

2.3. POWER BALANCE PERFORMANCE

To assess the thermal performance of a bifacial solar cell, we must calculate the radiative power balance of the system. Radiation emitted from the solar cell's surfaces escapes into space through Earth's atmosphere, while some is trapped by the surrounding atmosphere and contribute to the panel's thermal balance. During daylight hours, the solar cell's thermal power balance is significantly affected by the absorption of solar radiation in the 0.3 to 4 μm wavelength range. The final component of the radiative power balance is the absorbed non-radiative power from the surrounding environment, which primarily results from conductive and radiative thermal processes. Considering all of this, the thermal performance of the PERC bifacial solar cell is given by

$$P_{net} = P_r - P_a - P_{sun} - P_{nr} \quad (1)$$

where P_r is the radiated power from the cell, P_{sun} , and P_a are the absorbed irradiance by the cell from the sun and the atmosphere, respectively, and P_{nr} is the absorbed non-radiative power density from the surrounding. See more details in supplementary materials [47].

To determine the increase in thermal efficiency achieved by texturing the surfaces, we define a parameter for the difference in net thermal power. This parameter is obtained by subtracting the thermal power balance of the textured PERC bifacial solar cell from that of the flat one. We consider that the environmental conditions, the radiator thermal insulation, and wind speed for both samples are identical. Hence, the conduction and convection thermal process undergone by both bifacial solar cells is equal, and the non-radiative absorption terms cancel each other in the differential power balance. Considering this, Equation 1 expresses as follows:

$$P_{diff} = P_{net}^t - P_{net}^f = (P_r^t - P_r^f) - (P_a^t - P_a^f) - (P_{sun}^t - P_{sun}^f) \quad (2)$$

$$= \Delta P_r - \Delta P_a - \Delta P_{sun}$$

where the superscripts t and f refer to textured and flat samples, respectively. A positive differential net thermal power balance parameter (P_{diff} , as shown in Equation 2) is necessary to achieve a reduction in temperature through radiative cooling. To increase the power radiated (ΔP_r), texturization must be implemented while ensuring that the absorbed power from the sun and atmosphere remains equal or reduced. Conversely, a negative P_{diff} indicates additional thermal power absorption, which can increase the temperature of the solar cell and counteract the benefits of texturing.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present the results obtained trying to tailor the panel interfaces to optimize their performance in three wavelength intervals with different purposes: (i) the visible range, minimum reflection and maximum absorption by both sides, (ii) near-infrared, minimum absorption by both sides and (iii) atmospheric infrared, maximum emissivity in the side facing the sky. For this purpose, we have set up a simulation procedure to provide the electromagnetic performance (reflection, emission, and absorption) in the presented PERC bifacial panel.

3.1. OPTIMIZATION OF LIGHT ABSORPTION IN THE VISIBLE RANGE

Our primary objective is to optimize the surface texturing of the silicon layer to obtain the maximum generated photocurrent. According to its good performance observed in other studies [48–51], we have decided to use a texture of close-packed inverted pyramids with a period and height of 2 and 1.41 μm , respectively. Note that the angle of the inverted pyramids, 54.7°, is determined by the crystal structure of silicon (111) in microfabrication using lithography and etching [52]. We have studied the mutual influence of texturing on the front and rear sides by simulating the silicon layer illuminated from both sides. We have considered four cases, summarized in Fig. 2: a) a flat silicon wafer without texturing, b) a silicon wafer with textured top surface and flat rear side, illuminated from the front, c) a silicon wafer with a flat front side and textured rear side, illuminated from the rear side, and d) a silicon wafer with texturing on both sides, with illumination from one of them. We refer to direct incidence when the light strikes the front side and albedo incidence when it reaches the rear side.

Fig. 2. Schematic of simulated silicon wafers: (a) flat surfaces, (b) Square inverted pyramid texturing on the front side, (c) Square inverted pyramid texturing on the rear side, (d) Square inverted pyramid texturing on both sides. The height and period of the texture are labeled in (b) and are the same all cases. The Blue arrow represents the incident light direction.

Fig. 3 depicts the absorption spectra of a silicon wafer with and without texturing under direct (Fig. 2(b)) and albedo (Fig. 2(c)) light incidence. Albedo's Absorptivity has been calculated as average absorption spectra on the rear side from Lambert's cosine law, where the absorption spectrum for an incidence angle is weighted by its incidence angle. Hence, the average absorption can be calculated as,

$$\overline{A_{c-Si}(\lambda, \theta)} = \sum_{\theta=0}^n A_{c-Si}(\lambda, \theta) \cdot \cos\theta \quad (3)$$

where θ is the incidence angle of the albedo and $A_{c-Si}(\lambda, \theta)$ is the calculated absorptivity spectrum for an angle θ . The incidence angle of the albedo was swept from 0° to 70°, with a step of 10°. The presented results show that significant absorption enhancement is achieved when one of the silicon faces is textured. Specifically, the inverted pyramid pattern raises the absorptivity and average absorptivity values over the visible range for direct and albedo incidence by 17.8% and 3.8%, respectively, compared to the flat one.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra on (a) direct and (b) albedo incidence for a silicon wafer textured with inverted pyramids (solid black line) and a flat silicon wafer (red dashed line). The pitch and height of the inverted pyramids are 1.41 and 2, respectively.

Now, we examine the cross-influence when both sides are textured (Fig. 2(d)). We start by considering an unchanged front-side texture under direct incident but modifying the rear texturing. The front-side texturing is based on inverted pyramids with a pitch of 2 μm , while the rear one sweeps from a flat surface to four inverted pyramid patterns with a height of 1.41 μm and a period varying from 1 to 4 μm . The spectra shown in Fig. 4 indicate that the absorption in the visible range for direct incidence does not change significantly when the texturing on the rear side is modified. The differences in the absorption spectra arise from minor variations in the near-IR absorption response between 1 and 1.2 μm having an average absorptivity of both structures from 0.3 to 1.2 μm around 0.76 in all cases, with an error lower than 1%. Therefore, the absorption of the silicon layer can be considered independent of the rear-face texturing under direct incidence. Consequently, texturing optimization on the rear face should only focus on enhancing albedo absorption. This finding aligns with previous studies conducted on bifacial systems [53].

Fig. 4. Absorptivity of a 160 μm thickness silicon layer textured on the front side by inverted pyramids of pitch 2 μm , height 1.41 μm and varying the texturing of the rear one. The inverted pyramids on the rear side have the same height, 1.41 μm , and vary the pitch. The calculations were performed considering direct light incidence.

Fig. 5. Albedo's average absorptivity for a doubly textured silicon layer where the front side has inverted pyramids texturing of pitch $2 \mu\text{m}$ and height $1.41 \mu\text{m}$, and the rear side is modified.

Next, we analyze the contribution of albedo by using the previous silicon texturing patterns on both faces with the light now incident on the rear side (Fig. 2(d)). Fig. 5 shows the average absorption for each texturing pattern. As can we see, texturing enhances the absorption on the rear face in all cases. The average absorptivity increases by almost 15% in the best case (pitch of $1 \mu\text{m}$). Besides, the difference between average absorptivity is always lower than 4% as the period of textures varies. According to the obtained results, we can conclude that the optimization of silicon absorption by texturing can be designed independently for the light incidence on the front side, as no significant cross differences in improvement were observed. From previous results, we calculate a current density of 40.85 mA/cm^2 for direct incidence when silicon is textured on both sides (more details of these calculations are shown in the Supplementary materials [47]). The current density due to albedo depends on the ground material, with three typical substrates considered in solar cell applications: green grass (6.7 mA/cm^2), sand (18.4 mA/cm^2), and concrete (8.9 mA/cm^2). Therefore, the maximum current generated for the simulated bifacial textured cell reaches the value of 59.25 mA/cm^2 for the best case.

3.2. MIR RANGE RADIATIVE COOLING OPTIMIZATION

Solar panels under sun radiation reach operating temperatures above the ambient value. However, the conversion efficiency of a solar cell decreases as temperature rises, between 0.35 and $0.4 \text{ \%/}^\circ\text{C}$ [54]. Also, their durability suffers at higher temperatures. To reduce panel temperature, the maximization of radiative cooling is a promising strategy [55,56]. As this process occurs in the wavelengths of the atmospheric window ($8\text{-}13 \mu\text{m}$), its maximization requires the highest possible emissivity of the solar cell for these wavelengths. We propose to obtain it by texturing the encapsulating glass layer.

Fig. 6. Emissivity spectra of a flat glass sample (black solid line) and textured glass with pyramids (dashed red line). The calculations were carried out at normal incidence with infinite glass thickness.

As has been explained, and according to Equation (1), a radiator will only generate effective cooling when the output power exceeds the total absorbed one, resulting in a positive net cooling power. Ideally, the energy absorbed from the sun should be minimum in the 1.2 to 5 μm region, while the energy emitted in the transparent window spectrum should be maximum. In this study, we evaluated the thermal net power balance of the designed bifacial panel by introducing a glass texturing of square pyramids with height and pitch of 10 and 2 μm , respectively. Fig. 6 presents the calculated emissivity compared with the flat glass one. The texturing of the glass was selected based on the performance exhibited by square pyramids on the glass, as previously demonstrated [55]. As shown in Fig. 6, the emissivity for the textured glass is close to 1 in the considered range, similar to an ideal blackbody. The average emissivity through the atmospheric window (the integral of the absorptivity spectrum in the wavelength range 8–13 μm) for flat and textured glass is 0.87 and 1, respectively. Besides, a pyramid-textured glass does not present incidence directional emissivity changes in this range, which also helps to maximize the radiated power P_{rad} [55]. Therefore, the pyramid texturing pattern on glass performs significantly better than the flat one and may help reduce the thermal absorption of the system.

Fig. 7 Differential net cooling power (P_{diff}) from 5 to 25 μm as a function of temperature difference. The ambient temperature of each curve is indicated in the figure.

In the thermal power balance calculations, two ranges are considered: from 0.3 to 5 μm , dominated by the absorbed solar power (P_{sun}), and from 5 to 25 μm , dominated by the glass radiated power (P_{rad}). A fundamental factor in these calculations is the temperature difference (ΔT) between the ambient temperature (T_a) and the radiator temperature (T_r). Non-radiative power does not depend on the emissivity and its contribution cancels in Eq. (2). Fig. 7 shows the net power balance (P_{diff}) as a differential value between the net cooling power of the textured glass and the flat one. To demonstrate the effect of texturing on the power balance in the mid-infrared (MIR) range, we considered four typical ambient temperatures in a mid-latitude zone like Spain. In the case of solar cells, assuming the Nominal Maximum Operation Temperature (NMOT) of 60°C, the differential temperature (ΔT) is between 20 and 35°C under T_a . The best cooling performance at low ambient temperatures ($T_a=278.13\text{K}$) is 70 W/m². As T_a increases, despite the reduction in ΔT , the cooling capacity increases to around 100 W/m². Based on these results, it is possible to obtain an extra net cooling power, between 70 and 100 W/m², under daytime conditions by texturing the glass layers with the considered pyramids.

3.3. COMBINATION OF LIGHT-TRAPPING AND RADIATIVE COOLING STRATEGIES IN A PERC BIFACIAL SOLAR CELL

To complete the performance analysis, we now consider a PERC bifacial solar panel and calculate the absorptivity of the silicon considering all possible combinations of surface texturing. Several bifacial cells with different textured structures on silicon were analyzed. The results (see Supplementary material section [47]) showed that inverted pyramids was the best structure in terms of light trapping performance and was selected for the final panel design. Fig. 8 shows a cross-section of the PERC bifacial solar cells simulated: (a) all flat, (b) glass-textured with flat silicon, (c) flat glass with textured silicon, and (d) doubly textured bifacial panels (glass and silicon). Correspondingly, Fig. 9 presents the calculated absorptivity spectra for the exposed samples.

Fig. 8. Cross-section schematic of the modeled encapsulated PERC Bifacial solar cells NPP structure (the thickness of the layers has not been drawn to scale): (a) flat, (b) glass-textured but flat silicon, (c) Si-textured but flat glass, and (d) doubly textured.

The PERC panels with flat silicon exhibit significantly lower absorptivity regarding textured samples. The silicon texturing aimed to enhance light trapping, and this effect is not limited to visible light but extends to the NIR range (1.2 to 4 μm), where the increase is proportionally more significant. Glass texturing, on top of the silicon surface, offers an additional enhancement in visible absorptivity but not in NIR zone. In contrast, the absorptivity of the textured silicon panels is higher and more consistent along the spectra.

Fig. 9. Dependence of the silicon absorptivity on the BSC textures. (solid black line) flat BSC without textures, (dashed-red line) flat BSC with glass texturing, (dot-dashed blue line) silicon textured BSC, and (short-dashed green line) BSC with glass and silicon texturing. The results presented correspond to the normal incidence in all cases.

Next, we can compare the performance of each proposed PERC panel. Three different parameters need to be assessed: (i) the current gain, (ii) the sun heating power gained (0.3 to 5 μm), and (iii) MIR radiative cooling (5 to 25 μm). Therefore, we calculate three figures of merit normalized to a flat bifacial PERC panel. The first one is the normalized enhancement of total current density from 0.3 to 1.2 μm (direct and albedo), calculated as $\Delta J = (J_t - J_f) / J_f$. To calculate the albedo's current density, we consider a ground of sand. The second one is the thermal power balance from 0.3 to 5 μm in direct incidence, calculated as $\Delta P_{th} = P_{tht} - P_{thf}$. Finally, the third one is the differential net thermal power balance from 5 to 25 μm (ΔP_{diff}) with a T_r and T_a of 333K (corresponding to a 60°C operating temperature) and 298K, respectively. The subscripts t and f refer to textured and flat samples, respectively. The results are presented in Table 1, where J_f and P_{thf} are 49.7 mA/cm² and 553 W, respectively. Note that the current density and the thermal power balance values indicate inside the parentheses. The net power balance calculations for each analyzed structure can be found in the supplementary material section [47].

Sample\Figure of Merit	ΔJ (%)	ΔP_{th} (W)	ΔP_{diff} (W)
(b) Glass Textured flat-silicon BSC	4.4 % (52.0 mA/cm ²)	-24 W (577W)	95 W
(c) Flat-glass textured-silicon BSC	9.5 % (55.0 mA/cm ²)	-192 W (745W)	0 W
(d) Totally-textured BSC	15.3 % (58.8 mA/cm ²)	-179 W (732W)	95 W

Table 1. Summary of the current density, infrared thermal power gains, and net power balance in the MIR range for the textured PERC samples studied.

Considering the current density generated, the textured silicon and glass surfaces consistently outperformed their flat counterparts. As is seen in Fig. 8 (from left to right), the doubly textured structure (d) yielded the highest photocurrent gain of 15.3%. A similar trend was observed for the heat gain due to near-infrared solar radiation, which increased from 24 W to 179 W relative to the flat structure. Only the textured glass structures (b and d) generated a radiative cooling power of 95W. While all textured surfaces produced larger photocurrents, the thermal effects were not as clear. The heating caused by the near-infrared radiation was not offset by the cooling through the atmospheric window, resulting in a net power increase for all structures. To simplify the comparison of the panels, we present Table 2, which shows the combined thermal power of the entire spectrum and the current density changes as a percentage of the flat structure.

Current Gain	4.4 %	9.5%	15.3%
Thermal Gain	12.8%	-34.7%	-15.2%

Table 2. Summary of current density and net thermal power (from 0.3 to 25 μm) gains weighted by the flat PERC panel.

Only the flat silicon with textured glass offers a net power gain in both parameters, albeit a smaller one in photocurrent. On the other hand, the case of both textured materials, silicon, and glass, results in the maximum current density gain with a moderate thermal power loss.

To obtain a definitive assessment of panel efficiency for different structures, photonic and thermal effects must evaluate together. A relevant parameter is the cell efficiency degradation with temperature, which lies in the interval of 0.35-0.4% per degree Celsius. However, calculating the panel temperature requires a thermal model of the panel, which is outside the scope of this paper. Moreover, the results are dependent on atmospheric conditions and panel installation details. Therefore, we do not convert the thermal power (in watts per square meter) into actual temperature. Instead, we present two figures of merit, as shown in Table 2, which should combine for specific applications.

Moreover, the effect of the rear face of the bifacial panel is strongly dependent on the detailed characteristics of its panel installation, particularly on the reflectivity of the environment facing the back of the solar cell. The results presented in this section have been calculated for direct incidence, considering the solar power on the front side of the BSC. As previously shown, albedo incidence can generate extra current density up to 30% of the direct incidence. Besides, the ground's temperature, typically close to the ambient temperature, limits the radiated power of the glass by the rear side. Therefore, reliable figures of merit for the back face require many assumptions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have investigated the performance of bifacial solar panels with passivated emitter and rear cell (PERC) architecture under various configurations of the silicon surface (solar cell) and glass surface (encapsulation). We aimed to enhance light trapping and radiative cooling through computer simulations of different panel structures.

Our first significant result was that both faces of the panel have an independent performance since their cross-effects are negligible. Therefore, we can consider the four surfaces of the bifacial solar panel separately: the upper and lower sides of the silicon layer will determine the photon absorption (direct and albedo), while the glass layers will define the radiative cooling behavior.

Qualitatively we can conclude that silicon texturing significantly enhances light trapping. But this happens for all the spectrum, including the thermal power absorbed from the sun's near-infrared emission. On the other hand, encapsulating glass texturing increases the radiative cooling of the panel independently of the silicon surface. Considering both effects simultaneously, the thermal gain from the sun's near-infrared emission is greater than the radiated power in the atmospheric window, leading to higher temperatures.

In order to provide a quantitative assessment of the effects of the different surface configurations, we calculated figures of merit. From these values, we can conclude that:

- Texturing both surfaces (silicon and glass) results in a 15% increase in photocurrent and thermal power compared to a flat surface panel.
- The rear side of the panel can provide up to 30% extra current, but its thermal effect is highly dependent on installation details and atmospheric conditions.

The surface texturing strategies we studied are insufficient to achieve optimal light trapping and radiative cooling simultaneously. To achieve better thermal behavior while

maintaining visible light absorption, a surface that changes from maximum absorption in the visible spectrum to maximum reflectance in the near-infrared is necessary. However, such a surface would require more sophisticated and likely expensive alternatives, such as metasurfaces.

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